

Safeguard Mechanism in Jordan: Protection of Domestic Industry¹

Bashar H. Malkawi

The WTO Agreement on Safeguards prescribes each member to adopt appropriate domestic legislation before it imposes safeguard measures.² Historically, Jordan enacted its first WTO-compatible safeguard law, known as the National Production Protection Law No.4 of 1998 (“NPP Law”), in 1998 on the eve of Jordan’s accession to the WTO. Afterward, it amended its NPP Law of 1998. So now, Jordan’s safeguard system is based on the amended NPP Law No. 50 of 2002 and Regulation on Safeguard of National Production.³ The NPP Law of 2002 is a framework law that does not cover, as its name might suggest, all trade remedy legislations such as

* Bashar H. Malkawi is Dean and Professor of Law at the University of Sharjah, United Arab Emirates. He holds S.J.D in International Trade Law from American University, Washington College of Law and LL.M in International Trade Law from the University of Arizona.

¹ Discussion in this section will be limited to fair trade laws and regulations since Jordan invokes safeguard measures frequently and it has never applied an antidumping or countervailing duty order. Therefore, this section does not deal with antidumping, subsidies and countervailing regulations. Moreover, considerations of time and space do not permit for treating antidumping and countervailing laws and regulations. For more on unfair trade regulations see Provisional Anti-Dumping and Subsidies Regulation No. 26 of 2003, Official Gazette No. 4587 (March. 2, 2003). There could be a number of reasons for the passive use of antidumping or countervailing measures. First, the Jordanian market, until recently, was protected from foreign imports through high tariffs and other non-tariff trade barrier. Second, by the time of trade liberalization, some Jordanian industries may be adjusting to open market. Third, there could be lack of experience (legal, accounting, and human resources) in administering a complex anti-dumping or countervailing investigation and/or enforcing antidumping or countervailing duty orders. However, as more sectors in Jordan are opened to foreign competition, it becomes likely that some industries may petition the government to initiate antidumping or countervailing proceedings

² Jordan committed in its accession to the WTO that it would not apply an anti-dumping, countervailing, or safeguard measure to imports from WTO members until it had notified and implemented appropriate laws in conformity with the provisions of the WTO agreements on safeguards, subsidies and countervailing measures, and antidumping. See Working Party Report, *supra* note 223, at 107.

³ See Provisional Law on National Production Protection No. 50 of 2002, Official Gazette No. 4560 (August. 15, 2002). The new NPP Law is essentially modeled on the old NPP Law of 1998. However, the new NPP Law has been elaborated upon in terms of adding new articles such as article 3 which states explicitly that NPP Law of 2002 applies to agricultural as well as industrial products or new definitions such as that of like products and serious injury. See also Regulation on Safeguard of National Production No. 55 of 2000, Official Gazette No. 4465 (Nov. 16, 2000). The Regulation on Safeguard of 2000 has a total of thirty-nine articles. In these articles, the Regulation sets forth basic principles and concepts. It stipulates the conditions, investigation, forms, time limits, and review of safeguard measures.

antidumping and countervailing.⁴ In other words, the NPP Law No. 50 of 2002 is in fact neither an antidumping nor a countervailing duty law.

The organization in charge of the NPP Law is the Directorate of National Production Protection.⁵ In particular, the Safeguards Department, a non-independent organ under the umbrella of MIT, is in charge of administering safeguard cases.⁶ It conducts safeguard investigations with regard to serious injury caused by increase imports, recommends initiation of investigation, and relief measures.⁷ Although the Department may recommend to the minister of industry and trade a particular course of action in a safeguard investigation, its recommendation(s) may not be binding.⁸

Regarding the initiation of a safeguard proceeding, domestic producers or their representatives such as trade associations or chief administrative officials of the domestic producers are eligible to petition for investigation into an increase imports and serious injury.⁹ A complainant who petitions for investigation must submit the

⁴ Jordan had to follow up the adoption of the NPP Law with implementing regulations. It seems that Jordan was not able to counter-argue that no implementing regulations were needed given that the NPP Law contained description of investigation concepts such as injurious practices, increase imports, and serious and material injury.

⁵ The National Production Protection Directorate, which was set up in 2001, is divided into two departments: the Safeguards Department and the Anti-dumping Department (on file with author). There is also the Council on Tariff which is entrusted in recommending the application of safeguard measures to the Council of Ministers.

⁶ As of 2004, the Safeguards Department comprises seven permanent staff who presumably is appointed by the minister of industry and trade. It includes persons experienced in cost accounting and economics (on file with author).

⁷ See Regulation on Safeguard of National Production No. 55 of 2000, *supra* note 631, arts. 6, 11 & 23.

⁸ *Id.* arts. 10 & 11. The Safeguards Department's report to the minister is advisory. Thus, the minister can override any course of action recommended by the Department.

⁹ In order to restrict frivolous petitions, the Regulation on Safeguard defines domestic producers as those who produce the total number of domestic product or a major portion of the total amount of domestic production. Moreover, the regulation provides that a petitioner must not only be a member of the domestic producers, but also that firms accounting for no less than 25 percent of the total domestic production of the article involved must support the petition. *Id.* arts. 2, 7 & 11. Therefore, a prospective petitioner ought to persuade as many other firms as possible to join in the petition because the Department would be reluctant to institute an investigation unless the petition has broad support within the domestic producers. The Regulation does not recognize a union or a group of workers as an entity who may file a safeguard petition. This means that chief officials of the domestic producers are the ones who decide on petitioning. Additionally, the Regulation does not include the National Assembly as petitioner. However, according to article 35, it includes the ministry as a petitioner despite the fact that the Department is not at arm's length from the MIT. The record of the Safeguards Department indicates that it has never initiated a safeguard investigation on its own motion.

required documentary evidence and the application form along with additional items specified in the Regulation on Safeguard.¹⁰ Among the documents provided, those that are submitted on a confidential basis may not be open to the public without clear consent of the document provider.¹¹

The Regulation sets procedures for the execution of a safeguard investigation including time limits.¹² Once the Department initiates an investigation, it conducts the investigation by consulting sources such as surveys, administrative organs, hearing(s), and on-the-spot verifications.¹³ The hearing(s) held by the Department ought to be open to the public in principle, although the Regulation does not have a clear-cut provision on this matter, except when it is necessary to protect public interests or trade secrets.¹⁴ The Regulation contains a provision concerning public interest information supplied by downstream industrial users of the imported product or

¹⁰ A petitioner, in its filing, must set forth, the following information among others: (1) its identity (2) the identity of all known domestic producers of the domestic like product (3) the volume and value of the imported product (4) a description of the imported product (5) the name of each country in which the imported product originates (6) the identity of each known importer of the imported product and (7) the nature of its injury. *Id.* art. 8.

¹¹ The Department may not demand confidential documents but only a summary report. *Id.* art. 17. Non-confidential documents are generally made available and could be obtained from the reading room in MIT. An example of confidentiality would be to remove concrete numbers for the level of profits by whitening out the information when the Department publishes its edited version of the safeguard decision. However, excessive confidential designation for submitted documents could undermine the Department's ability to issue reasons for its decisions publicly. The current language of article 17 of the Regulation on Safeguard does not offer sufficient guidance on the treatment of confidential business documents. The Department may need to supplement its obligation of protecting commercially sensitive information by developing manuals that include, among other things, how information could be designated as confidential, destruction of documents related to confidential information within specific period after the conclusion of a case, separate protected and public files, signing a declaration of non-disclosure, access of domestic and foreign experts and counsels to documents, commitments of the Department's staff, and sanctions for any violation of confidentiality.

¹² When a petition of investigation is filed with the Department, the minister must decide within thirty days whether or not to initiate an investigation. Additionally, the investigation must be finalized within six months of its initiation. *Id.* arts. 10.a. See also Provisional Law on National Production Protection No. 50 of 2002, *supra* note 631, arts. 12.a.

¹³ See Regulation on Safeguard of National Production No. 55 of 2000, *supra* note 631, arts. 13, 14 & 16. The Safeguards Department as a whole conducts a safeguard investigation. Therefore, no special investigation team is formed.

¹⁴ To increase public participation, the investigative authority in Jordan may need to hold some fact-finding hearings in different cities. This will make it possible for citizens to participate in the decision-making process. Also, these out-of-Amman hearings would enable the media to cover trade matters more extensively.

consumers in safeguard investigation.¹⁵ For example, comments of the domestic coat industry would be taken into account in case being affected by the tariff increase on imports of leather that causes serious injury to the domestic leather industry. This would allow for broader public interest participation in safeguard investigation by determining whether other interests would be harmed by the imposition of safeguard measures.

The requirements for imposing safeguard measures include an increase in imports,¹⁶ the existence of serious injury to the domestic industry or threat thereof,¹⁷ and a causal relationship between the increase in imports and the injury.¹⁸ Additionally, if the Department recognizes that without urgent action the industry subject to the investigation may suffer irreparable harm, provisional relief measures may be recommended to the Council of Ministers.¹⁹ Although the Regulation on Safeguard of 2000 does not state whether a judgment on increase in imports or serious injury should pass by a majority vote of the Department's staff or by consensus, it is the practice that no voting occurs.

¹⁵ *Id.* art. 15. Public interest information provided could include the likely effects of safeguard measures on domestic producers that use the imported product as input in their production of other goods or the effects on competition in the domestic market.

¹⁶ The term should be construed here to include both absolute and relative increases in imports. *Id.* arts. 3& 6.a. This term is also specified in article 2.1 of the WTO Agreement on Safeguards. Increase in imports in absolute terms could be easily established compared with increase in imports in relative terms especially if the latter involves decline in imported quantities.

¹⁷ *Id.* art. 3.

¹⁸ The Regulation mentions, in particular, the rate and amount of increase imports as statistical correlation in investigating the casual relationship. *Id.* art. 6. However, it does not sufficiently describe methodologies for establishing a casual relationship between increase imports and serious injury when factors other than increase imports may cause serious injury. Therefore, it is important to establish procedures and criteria to analyze the casual relationship in a reasoned, clear, and adequate fashion. For example, the Department may need to study the entirety of factors causing serious injury by separating every factor and the effects of such factor so as to establish a genuine and substantial casual relationship.

¹⁹ *Id.* art. 20. According to the provisions of article 6 of the WTO Safeguards Agreement the duration of provisional emergency duties may not exceed two hundred days.

The Department can recommend that the minister takes certain relief measures for a designated period of time.²⁰ Based on the recommendations, the Council of Ministers finalizes the relief measures.²¹ The relief measures could be quotas, tariff-rate quota, or increase in tariffs.²² However, the Regulation does not include among relief measures assistance measures such as financial assistance and training.

The application of safeguard measures is limited to the extent of the injury caused by increase imports.²³ In other words, safeguard measures must not be applied to an extent beyond what is necessary to prevent or remedy serious injury and facilitate adjustment. The justification for such language is clear. The purpose of safeguard law is not to protect the domestic industry from unfair trade practices. If the pain inflicted on exporters by the application of safeguard measures is permitted to have effects beyond the share of injury caused by increase imports then this would mean that these exceptional remedies could be applied in a more restrictive manner than antidumping duties.

The duration of relief measures may not exceed four years.²⁴ However, it could be extended through a sunset review process for a period not exceeding ten years, included in the ten year the period of initial application. On record, no extension in the application of safeguard measures has been requested by Jordanian domestic

²⁰ The minister shall recommend to the tariff Council his decision. In turn, the Tariff Council recommends its decision to the Council of Ministers. *Id.* art. 23. Relief measures proposed by the Department have often been accepted by the minister.

²¹ The Council of Ministers must decide within thirty days of the minister's suggestions whether or not the relief measures will be implemented. See Provisional Law on National Production Protection No. 50 of 2002, *supra* note 631, art. 17.a. The NPP Law of 2002 does not specify whether in imposing a relief measure there must be evaluation of the impact of the relief measure on international trade relationships and the domestic economy.

²² See Regulation on Safeguard of National Production No. 55 of 2000, *supra* note 631, art. 25, 26 & 27. In Jordan, quotas restrictions could be more effective than tariff measures because the tariff rate increase may not significantly affect the total price for cheap imports.

²³ *Id.* art. 27.

²⁴ *Id.*

industries. It would be interesting to see whether future sunset reviews would lead to the continuation of safeguard measures as a *de facto* matter.

The Department should review the effectiveness of the relief measures.²⁵ Based on this analysis, the corresponding measures may be phased down or cancelled. In order to restrict indiscreet petitions, the Regulation provides that the Department shall not commence a second escape clause investigation of the same subject matter unless half the earlier safeguard measures period or two years have passed since the previous investigation, except if the new safeguard measures do not exceed 180 days.²⁶

The NPP Law of 2002 could also be applicable to products of non-WTO members.²⁷ For example, as a *de jure* matter, Jordan would apply its safeguard laws and regulations to imported products from Egypt since the latter is member of the WTO. On the other hand, Jordan may not rely on its laws to impose safeguard measure on imports from Lebanon since the latter is not yet a WTO member. However, as a *de facto* matter, nothing could prevent Jordan from imposing safeguard measures on imports from Lebanon especially that the latter is in the pipeline of acceding to the WTO.

Although the “rebalancing” principle is not addressed directly, article 33 of the Regulation contains it as required by article 8 of the WTO Agreement on Safeguards. It requires MIT to conduct prior consultations with interested WTO members before applying or extending definitive safeguard measures. The purpose of the “rebalancing” principle is to maintain a substantially equivalent level of concessions between a member imposing a safeguard measure and exporting members affected by

²⁵ *Id.* art. 30.

²⁶ *Id.* art. 28.

²⁷ See also Provisional Law on National Production Protection No. 50 of 2002, *supra* note 631, art. 3.b.

the measure.²⁸ Therefore, Jordan has to offer compensation for the adverse effects of a safeguard measure on trade of other WTO members.

Articles 32 and 38 of the Regulation made a special reference to developing countries. It exempts developing countries such as Egypt from the safeguard measure if their share of imports does not exceed three percent of total imports of the product covered by the measure. On this basis, an exporting developing country would argue that its own exports of the product covered by the safeguard measure represent less than 3 percent of the Jordanian market and therefore should not be subject to safeguard measures.

The Regulation addresses several issues of timing with regard to safeguard investigation and implementation. According to articles 12.1 of the WTO Agreement on Safeguards, the emphasis in notification is on “immediately”. Article 12 of the Regulation requires notification of Jordan’s initiation of a safeguard investigation. As an example, the probe on increase imports of aerated waters was launched on Sep. 17, 2002 and the WTO Safeguards Committee was notified the same day on Sep. 17, 2002.²⁹ A five or three-day delay between the time Jordan decides to apply safeguard measures and notification to the WTO could be acceptable. However, a 20-day wait could not be acceptable unless perhaps there are reasons that would justify such a delay.

²⁸ To achieve this, the members concerned may agree on any adequate means of trade compensation for the adverse effects of the measure on their trade. If no agreement on compensation is reached, the exporting members may proceed to suspend the application of “substantially equivalent concessions”. Normally, exercising the right to retaliate cannot occur during the first three years a safeguard measure is in place. However, retaliation can occur before then if the measure is found not to comply with the provisions of the Safeguards Agreement or if it was not in response to an absolute increase in imports. The right to retaliate under article 8 of the WTO Safeguards Agreement must be exercised with a 90 day period from the date the safeguard was imposed. However, in practice, nothing could prevent the country imposing the safeguard measure and other WTO members from reaching a procedural agreement on exercising the right to retaliate beyond the 90 day deadline.

²⁹ See Committee on Safeguards-Notification under Article 12.1(a) of the Agreement on Safeguards on Initiation of an Investigation and the Reasons for it-Jordan, Sep. 20, 2002, WTO Doc. No. G/SG/N/6/JOR/9.

One could argue that Jordan's NPP Law of 2002 and Regulation on Safeguard as being to large extent in accordance with the requirements of the WTO Safeguards Agreement, but there are several comments worth mentioning regarding Jordan's safeguard law and practice. The NPP Law defines domestic industry for purposes of a safeguard investigation. However, it does not address the case when a domestic producer imports and produces different kinds of products including the one subject to a safeguard investigation. Also an issue related to the definition of a domestic industry is whether or not domestic industry should be interpreted to include producers who have special arrangement, through joint ventures for example, with the importers or exporters where there is a coincidence of economic interests among them. Obviously, since Jordan is a small country, the case of a regionally dispersed industry, as supposed to national market, would not raise a controversy.³⁰ Therefore, Jordan would not have a regional industry.

With respect to serious injury in the agricultural sector, including perishable agricultural products, the NPP Law of 2002 and Regulation on Safeguard do not set specific factors to be considered in analyzing serious injury different from those of other industries. Special factors in investigating serious injury to agriculture industries could include whether there is an idling of cultivated land. The seasonal nature of agricultural products such as garlic, onion, and potatoes, which have a longer production period and a shorter sale period, merits special treatment. Therefore,

³⁰ In the U.S., in some instances the ITC may conduct a regional market analysis in dumping or countervailing duty investigations. See *Committee for Fairly Traded Venezuelan Cement v. United States*, 372 F.3d 1284, 1287-1288, 1290 (C.A. Fed. 2004) (in performing a regional market analysis, the ITC must find on a case-by-case basis a concentration of dumped imports into the regional market. In this context, the ITC must decide whether the ratio of subject imports to consumption is clearly higher in the regional market such as in Florida region than the rest of the U.S. market. Additionally, the ITC must find that imports in the region in question must account for a substantial portion of total subject imports entering the U.S.).

regarding investigating serious injury of agricultural industries, greater details are needed.

Jordan's NPP Law refers to manufactured as well as agricultural products in a safeguard investigation, but there is no reference to services.³¹ It seems that the current Law is not sufficient in addressing an injury to the domestic industry due to rapid import increase in services. One could interpret the absence of reference to services on the ground that MIT is a ministry, as its name indicates, concerned with "industry" while insurance and banking for example could fall under the jurisdiction of other government entities. Another interpretation is that a service safeguard could be unprecedented. As such, it would be a contentious issue in the WTO. At any rate, it is unclear how a service safeguard would work in practice because it requires a mechanism to track increasing imports which can be difficult in the case of services. The Regulation in article 30 requires the Department to submit a mid-term evaluation report of the relief measures. It seems that in few instances have relief measures been evaluated. Therefore, in order to apply the safeguard system constructively, the Department needs to evaluate whether or not the safeguard measures effected positive adjustment.³² This would help re-orienting of the NPP Law and Regulation from being simply a relief system to an adjustment system since safeguard measures are extraordinary measures to be taken only in emergency situations.

In principle, safeguard measures cannot be targeted at imports from a particular country and safeguard investigations should not be country specific. In other words, safeguard measures shall be applied to an imported product irrespective of its

³¹ A provision for a service safeguard would say that if import of services causes or threaten to cause serious injury to domestic industries that provide like or directly competitive services, the Department may adopt relief measures as necessary to remedy such injury or threat thereof.

³² Examples of positive adjustment include consolidation, increase investment, transfer of resources to different products along the production line, or transfer resources to different industries all together.

source.³³ However, in the case of China, a safeguard measure could be country/product-specific.³⁴ Therefore, Jordan may want to implement paragraph 16 of China's Protocol of Accession to the WTO into domestic law.

One other point that is currently missing in the Jordanian Regulation on Safeguard of 2000 is any mention of article XIX of GATT 1994.³⁵ For example, there is no reference in the Regulation of the circumstance of "unforeseen developments" as stipulated by article XIX.1(a) of GATT 1994. This circumstance is a prerequisite for imposing a safeguard measure before meeting other conditions.³⁶ As it stands, the Department is not obliged by the NPP Law of 2002 or the Regulation to examine the existence of "unforeseen developments" in its investigation.³⁷ Requiring a WTO

³³ See Provisional Law on National Production Protection No. 50 of 2002, *supra* note 631, art. 19.

³⁴ Paragraph 16 of China's Protocol of Accession provides that where products of Chinese origin are being imported into the territory of any WTO Member in such increased quantities or under such conditions as to cause or threaten to cause "market disruption" to the domestic producers of like or directly competitive products, the WTO Member so affected may request consultations with China with a view to seeking a mutually satisfactory solution, including whether the affected WTO Member should pursue application of a measure under the Agreement on Safeguards. If consultations do not lead to an agreement between China and the WTO Member concerned within 60 days of the receipt of a request for consultations, the WTO Member affected "shall be free", in respect of such products, to withdraw concessions or otherwise to limit imports only to the extent necessary to prevent or remedy such market disruption. The application of China's safeguard provision shall be terminated 12 years after the date of accession. See Accession of the People's Republic of China, Nov. 23, 2001, WTO Doc. No. WT/L/432, para. 16. Rather than adopting a "market disruption" standard, the WTO Agreement on Safeguards in article 2.1 requires that a product is being imported under such conditions as to cause or threaten to cause "serious injury" to the domestic industry.

³⁵ The WTO Agreement on Safeguards and article XIX of GATT 1994 must be read cumulatively. This is supported by article 1 of the WTO Agreement on Safeguards which states that the Agreement establishes rules for the application of safeguard measures which shall be understood to mean those provided for in article XIX of GATT 1994.

³⁶ According to some commentators, earlier in the history of article XIX of GATT, the requirement of "unforeseen development" was not required. See Ezra Ginzburg, *An Analysis of Article XIX: The Safeguard Problem after the Uruguay Round*, 17 NEB. L. REV. 566, 568 (1992) (the unforeseen development requirement has little meaning. It has been read out of existence under the GATT). However, recent WTO Appellate Body decisions have restored the requirement of "unforeseen developments" in applying safeguard measures. See Report of the Appellate Body, United States-Safeguard Measures on Imports of Fresh, Chilled or Frozen Lamb Meat from New Zealand and Australia, May. 1, 2001, WTO Doc. No. WT/DS177/AB/R, para. 69.

³⁷ In actuality, the Department had factored "unforeseen developments" requirement in all safeguard cases it examined. However, this practice may not be satisfactory until the Regulation is amended to explicitly make reference to "unforeseen developments" requirement. The WTO Appellate Body in the Lamb case rejected the U.S. argument that the "unforeseen developments" needed to justify a safeguard measure could be inferred from the factual record of the investigating authority and demonstrated during WTO dispute settlement proceedings. See United States-Safeguard Measures on Imports of Fresh, Chilled or Frozen Lamb Meat, *supra* note 663, at paras. 67 & 74. Sources in the

member to establish import surges as “unforeseen developments” as a condition for its application of safeguards could make it difficult for a member to utilize safeguard measures since such import surges may not easily be said to be unforeseen.

Proper and accurate translation seems to be an issue to NPP Law and Regulation on Safeguard in Jordan.³⁸ Mistranslation or literal translation could affect the application of the NPP Law. For example, precision in translating one of the most important terms in the safeguard provisions, serious injury, could pose a problem. One should not regard mistranslation of certain terms as inconsequential. Inaccurate or deliberate misleading translations of WTO safeguard provisions may make the translated law or regulation subject to criticism by other trading partners. Therefore, Jordan would have to update its vocabularies to reflect the WTO Safeguards Agreement so equivalents for words of the Agreement are available.

In effect, Jordan adopted the unified system in its safeguard law. In other words, one organ, the Safeguards Department, is the one which investigates increase imports and serious injury to the domestic industry.³⁹ This is reasonable because the Department would perform its function quickly and efficiently. On the other hand, it could be disadvantageous because the investigation of increase imports and the judgment of injury may lack objectivity by centralizing the authority into the same Department.

Jordan, in its attempt to improve its regime of safeguard measures, must take note that the WTO Agreement on Safeguards is a procedural agreement establishing

Safeguards Department indicated that it currently prepares a draft regulation implementing the requirement of “unforeseen developments”.

³⁸ See Committee on Anti-Dumping Practices-Committee on Subsidies and Countervailing Measures-Notification of Laws and Regulations under Articles 18.5 and 32.6 of the Agreements, June 8, 2004, WTO Doc. No. G/ADP/N/1/JOR/2/Corr.1 (stating that a material error affected the translation of article 11(a) (2) [in the NPP Law of 2002] as the word “public” was replaced by “personal”). Certain linguistic characteristics such as the use of passive voice sentences and different tenses could contribute to further problems in translation.

³⁹ This is compared with the dual system in which two organs, whether independents or not, conduct the investigation of increase imports and the judgment of an injury.

certain minimal procedural requirements.⁴⁰ It does not have to adhere to the exact words of certain provisions of the Safeguards Agreement. In other words, Jordan could modify its law in a way that is different from the Agreement. The WTO Agreement on Safeguards permits the use of safeguard for up to eight or ten years. However, for example, Jordan could only have it for three years. Moreover, Jordan must take into account the WTO panel decisions. For example, recent WTO panel decisions have brought to life the requirement of “unforeseen developments” or require the competent authority to provide “explicit” findings that are “clear and unambiguous” and “do not merely imply or suggest an explanation”.⁴¹

To meet the future demand of relief measures, Jordan must put in place a plan to help small and medium-sized firms access the safeguard system. The current system may pose problems for these companies in terms of the costs of complying with the Law or Regulation requirements including paper burden, formality, complexity, and duration of the process, lack knowledge and expertise about safeguard law and its procedures, the need to work with other small producers or producer association, and the cost of hiring external counsels.

The Safeguard Department may want to self-initiate safeguard investigation rather than wait for domestic industry to petition for it. Self-initiation of safeguard investigation may enable the Safeguard Department to limit imports more quickly. If the domestic industry petitions for safeguard measures, it would take longer time to impose restrictions on imports because the safeguard investigation would require

⁴⁰ The WTO Agreement on Safeguards does not impose a simple arithmetic standard for determining increased imports or requires a certain pattern of imports.

⁴¹ None of these terms appears in article 3.1 of the WTO Agreement on Safeguards which requires only publication of the findings and reasoned conclusions reached on all pertinent issues of fact and law. The ordinary meaning of these terms does not establish any level of clarity for the competent authority or require that it states its findings with a particular explicitness.

longer process. Therefore, self-initiation of safeguard investigation could produce faster results by cutting time needed to conduct an investigation.

Courts in Jordan have not developed an extensive jurisdiction in the area of trade remedy laws. This may be interpreted to the inexperience of Jordan's courts in reviewing remedy law cases. Another interpretation would be that Jordan's trade remedy system is a relatively young one (Jordan did not have an antidumping regulation until 2003).

Based on data collected in February 2003, fourteen investigations on the application of safeguard measures have been either self-initiated by the competent authority or initiated upon petition from the domestic industries of Arab countries members of the WTO. Egypt, Jordan, and Morocco are the frequent users of safeguard provisions. Of those fourteen petitions, Jordan has investigated nine, Egypt has investigated three, and Morocco has investigated two. Of Jordan's petitions, the competent authority found serious injury in four, terminated four, and there is one outstanding investigation.⁴² Of the three petitions of Egypt, the competent authority found merit in all of them.⁴³ Of the two petitions of Morocco, the competent authority

⁴² Jordan found serious injury and applied safeguard measures on imports of biscuits and chocolates, (Aug. 24, 2001, WTO Doc. No. G/SG/N/8/JOR/1, WTO Doc. No. G/SG/N/10/JOR/1), imports of unrecorded media tapes (magnetic tapes) for sound recording or similar recording of other phenomena of a width not exceeding 4 mm, (June 19, 2002, WTO Doc. No. G/SG/N/8/JOR/2/Corr.1, WTO Doc. No. G/SG/N/10/JOR/2/Corr.1), imports of pasta in all its forms, (Jan. 27, 2003, WTO Doc. No. G/SG/N/8/JOR/3, Feb. 24, 2003, WTO Doc. No. G/SG/N/10/JOR/3), imports of sanitary products in all its forms and specifications, (Jan. 31, 2003, WTO Doc. No. G/SG/N/8/JOR/4, Feb. 21, 2003, WTO Doc. No. G/SG/N/10/JOR/4). Jordan terminated safeguard investigation on chocolate containing over 5 percent of coconut butter substitute, (July 3, 2001, WTO Doc. No. G/SG/N/9/JOR/1), imports of cooking appliances and plate-warmers - for gas fuel or for both gas and other fuels, (Oct. 31, 2002, WTO Doc. No. G/SG/N/9/JOR/4, G/SG/N/9/JOR/5), electric accumulators, including separators thereof, whether or not rectangular (including square) lead-acid, of a kind used for starting piston engines, (Oct. 31, 2002, WTO Doc. No. G/SG/N/9/JOR/3), and imports of Unglazed ceramic flags and paving, hearth or wall tiles; unglazed ceramic mosaic cubes and the like, whether or not on a backing and glazed ceramic flags and paving (Oct. 31, 2002, WTO Doc. No. G/SG/N/9/JOR/2). There was an outstanding investigation on imports of aerated waters containing added sugar or other sweeteners or flavors (Sep. 20, 2002, WTO Doc. No. G/SG/N/6/JOR/9).

⁴³ Egypt found serious injury on imports of matches, (Aug. 11, 1998, WTO Doc. No. G/SG/N/7/EGY/1, Feb. 10, 1999, WTO Docs. No. G/SG/N/8/EGY/1, G/SG/N/10/EGY/1), imports of Common Fluorescent Lamps, (Mar. 1, 2000, WTO Docs. No. G/SG/N/8/EGY/2, G/SG/N/10/EGY/2,

imposed safeguard measures in one and terminated the other without imposing any safeguard measure.⁴⁴ Thus, almost 80 percent of the petitions resulted in import restrictions. Other Arab countries members of the WTO have not taken any safeguard action.⁴⁵

Since their accession to the GATT/WTO, many Arab countries still impose safeguard measures as trade remedy measures. There have been no major structural changes in their respective trade remedy policies. If the purpose is to protect Arab countries' industries, then it is more advantageous to use antidumping and countervailing duty laws. For example, if Jordan uses its antidumping law to protect its domestic industry, it can target a particular industry of a country rather than imposing a safeguard measure against all countries as required by article 2.2 of the WTO Agreement on Safeguards. In this way, Jordan will not upset its trade relationship with other countries. Moreover, Jordan does not need to provide compensation to the exporting country(s) in the case of imposing antidumping duty, while under article 8.1 of the WTO Agreement on Safeguard Jordan has to maintain the same level of concession in case it imposes a safeguard measure. Finally, by imposing an antidumping duty Jordan will tell the world that its industries are just as competitive but because other countries dump in its market, it cannot compete. On the other hand, if Jordan imposes a safeguard measure, that is similar to saying "we

Feb. 28, 2001, WTO Docs. No. G/SG/N/8/EGY/3, G/SG/N/10/EGY/3), and imports of Powdered Milk (Sep. 26, 2000, WTO Doc. No. G/SG/N/7/EGY/2, Apr. 3, 2001, WTO Doc. No. G/SG/N/8/EGY/4, G/SG/N/10/EGY/4).

⁴⁴ Morocco took safeguard measures on the importation of Bananas (Nov. 1, 2000, WTO Doc. No. G/SG/N/7/MAR/1, May 22, 2001, WTO Doc. No. G/SG/N/8/MAR/1, G/SG/N/10/MAR/1). Morocco terminated the investigation without applying any safeguard measure on rubber plate and sheet products (Jan. 10, 2002, WTO Doc. No. G/SG/N/9/MAR/1).

⁴⁵ See for instance UAE (Feb. 3, 1998, WTO Doc. No. G/SG/Q1/ARE/2), Bahrain (Jan. 16, 1998, WTO Doc. No. G/SG/Q1/BHR/2, 13. Oct. 2000, WTO Doc. No. Para. 26. WT/TPR/M/74), Qatar (Jan. 12, 1999 WTO Doc. No. G/SG/Q1/QAT/2), Oman (Apr. 10, 2001 WTO Docs. No. G/ADP/N/1/OMN/1, G/SCM/N/1/OMN/1, G/SG/N/1/OMN/1), and Tunisia (Sep. 11, 2001, WTO Docs. No. G/ADP/Q1/TUN/5, G/SCM/Q1/TUN/5).

confess and declare that our industries are not competitive, so would you please give us more time". Bluntly, safeguard law is a weak defense measure for weak countries. Based on reports submitted to WTO committees in various periods, no Arab country undertook antidumping duty actions.⁴⁶ Egypt is the only Arab country member of the WTO that has taken an antidumping or countervailing duty action.⁴⁷ Thus, history shows that Egypt is the only Arab country that has launched and imposed antidumping measures.⁴⁸ This is ironic considering that other countries, such as the U.S., imposes antidumping and countervailing duties on exports of Arab countries. For example, the U.S. has imposed countervailing duty on imports of carbon steel wire rods from Saudi Arabia.⁴⁹ The EC has also imposed antidumping orders of 40 percent on imports of urea from Libya and Saudi Arabia.⁵⁰

In its accession negotiations, Jordan attempted to apply for certain agricultural products such as olive oil, sheep, and poultry meat as special safeguard goods (SSG).⁵¹ If Jordan were able to designate those agricultural products as SSG, the

⁴⁶ See Committee on Subsidies and Countervailing Measures, *Semi-Annual Reports under Article 25.11 of the Agreement*, G/SCM/N/52/Add.1/Rev.5 (Oct. 18, 2002).

⁴⁷ For example from the period 1996-2002 the following countries have submitted reports on whether a countervailing duty action has been taken or not: Kuwait, Morocco, Qatar, Tunisia, and United Arab Emirates. No reports have been received from the following Members: Bahrain, Djibouti, and Mauritania. See G/SCM/N/19/Add.1/Rev.10.

⁴⁸ See Press Release, WTO Secretariat Reports Significant Decline in Anti-Dumping Investigations, PRESS/374 (Apr. 20, 2004) (the WTO Secretariat stated that in the later part of 2003 115 investigations had been initiated. On the other hand, final antidumping duty orders imposed remained relatively constant. For example, over the same period in 2002 there were 113 final antidumping orders compared with 107 final orders in 2003).

⁴⁹ The case involved Saudi Iron and Steel Co. challenging the USITA methodology for determining the amount of Saudi subsidy, loan in that case. See *Georgetown Steel Corp. v. U.S.* 810 F.Supp. 318 (Ct. Intl. Trade 1992).

⁵⁰ The European Court of Justice overruled the antidumping order on the basis that the defendants were denied access to information. See Case C-49/88, *Al-Jubail Fertilizer Co. & others v. Council*, 1991 E.C.R. I-03187 (1991).

WTO Agreement on Agriculture would have applied to them.⁵² However, Jordan was not able to designate olive oil, sheep, and poultry as SSG. Instead, WTO working party members determined whether a product of an acceding country such as Jordan merited designation as SSG or not but not for Jordan itself. Other WTO members were concerned that if Jordan was able to designate certain agricultural products as SSG, it would set a precedent for future acceding countries who would request designating their own agricultural products as SSG. This would have created a situation that seemed to be unacceptable for members of the working party on Jordan's accession to the WTO.

Trade Remedy Measures of the US-JO FTA

According to the US-JO FTA, parties can apply safeguard measures based on bilateral or global basis.⁵³ Either party can take safeguard measures against

⁵¹ Even after Jordan acceded to the WTO, Jordan argues for SSG designation for olive oil, sheep, and poultry meat. See Proposal by Jordan, *WTO Negotiations on Agriculture*, G/AG/NG/W/140 (Mar. 22, 2001) (page references are not avail.).

⁵² Article 5 of the WTO Agreement on Agriculture is a special safeguard article for agricultural products. However, in order to apply this special safeguard provision, any non-tariff measure imposed on the imported agriculture product in question would have to be converted into tariff. Additionally, the agricultural product must be designated as SSG. Moreover, there are two conditions the presence of either one of them is sufficient to trigger the special safeguard. First, the volume of imported agricultural product will have to exceed a trigger level. Second, the price of imported agricultural product must fall below the trigger price in the base period (1986-1990). If the first condition is satisfied, then an additional duty will be applied for the rest of the year in question (the additional duty may not exceed 33.3% of the ordinary tariff in effect the year the action was taken). If the second criterion is met, then additional duty will be imposed on a shipment-by-shipment basis. Article 5 of the WTO Agreement on Agriculture is a special provision since it does not require a serious injury test, the safeguard measure will in the form of additional duty only, and no retaliation is allowed. This is contrary to the WTO Safeguards Agreement which requires an injury test, a safeguard measure could be in the form of tariff or quota, and there could be counter-retaliation. In order to obtain SSG status, an acceding country has to convert non-tariff trade measures into tariffs. Jordan did not convert non-tariff trade measures into tariffs as required under article 4 of the WTO Agreement on Agriculture, a condition that is vital for applying SSG measure. Rather, Jordan set tariffs on agricultural imports at lower levels and bound them.

⁵³ The terms safeguard measures, escape clause, and emergency actions are interchangeable. Chapter eight of NAFTA is titled "emergency action". See NAFTA, *supra* note 697, at 383. They carry the meaning that a country can escape its obligations of a free trade agreement under certain conditions. NAFTA also establishes two safeguard actions. Safeguard actions can be imposed on "originating goods" from NAFTA region that are imported in such quantities that cause or threaten to cause serious injury. Additionally, NAFTA party can impose safeguard measures on imported goods from "all countries", including NAFTA region. *Id.* arts. 801& 802.

originating goods of the other party in situations in which such goods may cause or threaten to cause serious injury. The imposition of a safeguard measure under the FTA is tied to obligations. There must be a link between increased imports and the FTA's tariff concessions.⁵⁴ However, such a link is subject to a proviso that "only" the reduction or elimination of a duty is a "significant cause" that leads to an increase in imports, but need not be equal to or greater than any other cause.⁵⁵ The requirement that tariff concession be a "significant cause" of increased imports is extracted from U.S. law.⁵⁶ To impose a safeguard measure, Jordan will have to meet what could be christened as "double test". First, Jordan must prove that tariff concession is a "significant cause" of increased imports.⁵⁷ If successful, then Jordan will have to prove that increased imports are "substantial cause" of serious injury. There is a presumption that increased imports are not the result of tariff concessions, unless proven otherwise.

To impose safeguard measures under the FTA there must be an importation of goods in increased quantities, in either absolute or relative terms.⁵⁸ Moreover, imports of goods must constitute a "substantial cause" of serious injury, or threat thereof to a domestic industry that produce like or directly competitive product. The term

⁵⁴ See United States (U.S.)-Jordan: Agreement Between The United States of America and the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan on The Establishment of a Free Trade Area, *supra* n. 695, art.10.1.

⁵⁵ *Id.*

⁵⁶ See *Trade Act of 1974*, 19 U.S.C. § 2436 (2000). Section 406 of the Trade Act permits safeguard measures to counter market disruption from communist countries where rapid imports is "significant cause", but need not be equal to or greater than any other cause, of material injury.

⁵⁷ Absence the test for the link between tariff concession and increase imports, the safeguard provision of the US-JO FTA would be a mere measure for determining what is an unacceptable level of imports without the need to meet such a difficult test. Moreover, "significant cause" is not defined in the FTA. Is it the same as "substantial cause", less, or more? Does significant cause require cut-off such as 50 percent or 60 percent threshold among other causes? Significant cause requires analysis on a case-by-case basis.

⁵⁸ Under NAFTA, a party may impose a safeguard measure if there is increase in import in absolute quantities only. See NAFTA, *supra* n. 697, art. 801. 1.

“substantial cause” is defined as a cause that is “important” and “not less than any other cause,” a definition derived directly from U.S. trade remedy law.⁵⁹ According to this definition of substantial cause, two prongs must be met. First, imports must be an “important” cause of serious injury. Second, imports must be “not less than any other cause”. This “substantial cause” test has so difficult to overcome that section 201 of the the U.S. Trade Act has fallen largely into disuse. Aggrieved industries now rely upon the less stringent burdens of the countervailing and antidumping provisions of U.S. trade law to address injuries and threats from imports.⁶⁰

Under the FTA, a safeguard measure may be imposed for a period of time no more than four years.⁶¹ After the expiration of the transition period for imposing a safeguard measure, neither party can impose such a measure unless the other party consents. One can reason that this discrepancy in the ability to apply a safeguard measure without consent during the transition period and the requirement of obtaining consent after the transition period is based on the thought that the free trade area formed by the US-JO FTA would make a safeguard measure less necessary. It is also

⁵⁹ Section 201 of the U.S. trade act of 1974 permits imports to be restricted, for a limited time, and on a non-discriminatory basis, if they are substantial cause of serious injury to U.S. firms or workers. Under the U.S. Trade Expansion Act of 1962, imports must have been “the major factor” causing injury. The Tariff Commission, now called the ITC, has interpreted this to mean that the increased imports were a more important cause of injury than all other causes combined. It is obvious that this interpretation was too restrictive. See Peter Bernardi, *The Great Escape*, 7 D.C.L. J. Intl. L. & Prac. 69, 80 (1998). By adopting, the substantial causation test, the U.S. Congress intended to provide a lower burden of proof than that contained in the 1962 Trade Expansion Act. Moreover, article 2 of the WTO Agreement on Safeguards allows a member to apply a safeguard measure to a product only if that member has determined that such product is being imported into its territory in such increased quantities as to “cause” or threaten to cause serious injury to domestic industry. It is noticeable the absence of “substantial cause” from the language of the WTO Agreement on Safeguards.

⁶⁰ The only success story recalled for section 201 petitions is Harley-Davidson case of 1983 of imposing tariffs on inventories of motorcycles from Japan of 700cc models. See Annual Report of the United States International Trade Commission 1-2 (1983) (tariffs increased on completed heavyweight motorcycles by 45 percent *ad valorem*, declining to 35, 20, 15, and 10 in subsequent years). In 1987, before the end of the safeguard protection period, Harley-Davidson requested the termination of the safeguard since the company has adjusted to competition from Japan.

⁶¹ United States (U.S.)-Jordan: Agreement Between The United States of America and the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan on The Establishment of a Free Trade Area, *supra* n. 695, art. 10.2.d.ii.

thought that local industries will have adjusted to trade competition by the time that the transition period ends.

Article 10 of the US-JO FTA establishes procedural obligations for conducting a safeguard investigation and providing notification and consultation with respect to that investigation.⁶² The US-JO FTA stipulates that an investigation must be conducted by a competent authority.⁶³ For purposes of conducting an investigation, the US-JO FTA also incorporates some provisions of the WTO Agreement on Safeguard. For example, while conducting an investigation, either party to the FTA must provide reasonable public notice, a public hearing, and publish a report that sets forth the “findings” and “reasoned conclusions” reached on all pertinent issues of facts and laws. Moreover, either party to the FTA must evaluate all relevant factors of an “objective and quantifiable” nature that have a bearing on the situation of the industry seeking protection.

The US-JO FTA covers “global action” safeguards.⁶⁴ Any safeguard measure imposed according to the “global action” provision must comply with the requirements of article XIX of GATT 1994 and the WTO Agreement on Safeguard. Any safeguard measure must be applied on a MFN basis.⁶⁵ The “global action” provision allows a party to impose a safeguard against the other as part of a multilateral safeguard action taken under article XIX of the GATT and WTO safeguard agreement. However, imports of one party to the FTA may be excluded from an MFN safeguard measure if such imports are not a substantial cause of serious injury

⁶² *Id.* art.10.2.c.

⁶³ *Id.* 10.2.

⁶⁴ “Each Party retains its rights and obligations under Article XIX of GATT 1994 and the WTO Agreement on Safeguards”. *Id.* art.10.8.

⁶⁵ “Safeguard measures shall be applied to a product being imported irrespective of its source”. See WTO Agreement on Safeguard, art. 2.1.

or threat thereof. The FTA is silent as to whether imports from a party alone constitute substantial cause of serious injury to the domestic industry, what should the form of the safeguard measure be, or the type of compensation to be provided.⁶⁶ The FTA parties could have agreed that imports less than 10 percent of total imports would not be considered substantial.

The US-JO FTA has an industrial policy language aimed at protecting some industries that initially cannot offer competitive prices and quality as competing imports but nonetheless by giving them breathing room can develop over time into competitive price and quality industries.⁶⁷ An infant industry is defined, in the US-JO FTA, as an industry that has recently begun to produce like or directly competitive product. It is not clear whether the infant industry provision applies to infant industries that existed prior to the conclusion of the FTA or is limited only to infant industries established after the FTA came into existence. Based on the FTA language, an infant industry is a new industry. This definition does not include an already established industry that produces a new line of product or an expansion of an already existing industry supplying small proportion of the domestic market, or an industry that had previously been destroyed as a result of hostilities or natural disasters. The definition of an infant industry has a narrow scope.⁶⁸

⁶⁶ Under NAFTA for example, in order to determine in global action whether imports from NAFTA party are substantially cause serious injury to the domestic industry, imports from that NAFTA party must be among the top five suppliers of the good. See NAFTA, *supra* n. 697, art. 802. 2.a.

⁶⁷ The FTA states that the Parties recognize that, because it has recently begun to produce a like or directly competitive product described in paragraph 1 [originating good of the other party], an infant industry may face challenges that more mature industries do not encounter. As such, each Party shall ensure that the procedures described in paragraph 2 [the procedures for safeguard investigation] do not create obstacles to infant industries that seek the imposition of such measures". See United States (U.S.)-Jordan: Agreement Between The United States of America and the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan on The Establishment of a Free Trade Area, *supra* n. 695, art. 10.5.

⁶⁸ The definition of an infant industry in article XVIII.2 of GATT 1994 is broader. It includes new industry, a new branch of production in an existing industry, substantial transformation of an existing

The FTA infant industry provision suggests that Jordan can shield its domestic industries by keeping out U.S. competitors. Depending on how a panel may interpret the infant industry provision, the provision may be found to have little value. First, even assuming that the FTA gives preferential consideration for Jordan's infant industry preferential treatment is limited to procedures used in conducting a safeguard investigation. In other words, the investigation authority in Jordan may give an infant industry more time to respond for a request for a public hearing, present its evidence, or provide a counter-argument against an exporter or importer. The preferential treatment does not mean that an infant industry will be guaranteed a positive determination by imposing a safeguard measure. Second, the ultimate purpose of the US-JO FTA is to liberalize trade; the industrial policy article is at odds with this objective. While article XVIII of GATT 1994 allows additional facilities for infant industry such as tariff protection, government assistance through non-tariff measures, and subsidies, the FTA 's infant industry provision restricts in scope and time Jordan's ability to provide protection for its infant industries.⁶⁹

The only import relief mechanisms available under the US-JO FTA are safeguard measures. The FTA does not have a provision on antidumping or countervailing duties. The inclusion of a safeguard measures under the US-JO FTA reflects the U.S. requirement that all trade agreements must have, at minimum, a provision for

industry, expansion of an existing industry supplying a relatively small proportion of domestic demand, and an industry destroyed or substantially damaged as a result of hostilities or natural disasters.

⁶⁹ The discussion has focused so far on the assumption that the FTA article applies only to infant industry of Jordan. The question that arises is whether the FTA infant industry language applies also to the U.S. which is often acknowledged as having no industrial policy. See *Fair Trade and Harmonization: Prerequisites for Free Trade* 306-309 (Jagdish Bhagwati & Robert E. Hudec eds., MIT Press

1996) (the United States has not had an avowed industrial policy. However, some critics have contended that the U.S. does in fact have an industrial policy in the broad sense. The U.S. has an implicit and decentralized industrial policy. The U.S. government and laws do advantage some industries over others).

safeguard measures.⁷⁰ Thus, the US-JO FTA leaves domestic antidumping and countervailing duty laws untouched.

⁷⁰ Following World War II, the U.S. president continued this policy by issuing an executive order requiring the presence of an escape clause in all future trade agreements. See Paul C. Rosenthal & Robin H. Gilbert, *The 1988 Amendments to Section 201: It is not Just for Import Relief Anymore*, 20 Law & Policy Intl. Bus. 403, 406 (1989).